

Tuberculous abscess of the thyroid gland with compressive symptoms: a case report

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Abstract

Introduction: Thyroid involvement by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is uncommon and may mimic neoplasia or subacute thyroiditis. Diagnostic delay is frequent because cytology from the thyroid gland can be non-diagnostic, and clinical features overlap with other inflammatory and malignant conditions.

Case report: A 70-year-old woman with pulmonary tuberculosis presented with several weeks of progressive right-sided neck swelling, dyspnoea and odynophagia, accompanied by night sweats and weight loss (~10 kg over three months). Examination revealed a 5-cm right neck mass (level II) and a palpable supraclavicular node; thyroid function was normal. Ultrasonography demonstrated a 5-cm thyroid lesion. Fine-needle aspiration of the thyroid was non-diagnostic, whereas aspiration of a supraclavicular node confirmed tuberculosis. Owing to compressive symptoms and suspected suppuration, surgical drainage with total thyroidectomy was undertaken; specimens were submitted for histopathology.

Discussion: Thyroid tuberculosis, though rare, should be considered in endemic settings and in patients with systemic risk factors. Image-guided sampling of cervical lymph nodes can increase diagnostic yield when thyroid cytology is equivocal. Management is primarily medical with standard anti-tuberculous therapy; surgery is reserved for large abscesses, airway compromise, failure of percutaneous control or diagnostic uncertainty. This case illustrates the value of targeted sampling, timely source control and multidisciplinary care.

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Introduction

Thyroid tuberculosis is a rare manifestation of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection despite the gland's rich vascularity, lymphatic drainage and iodine content, which are thought to confer relative resistance to infection¹. Clinical presentations range from solitary nodules to diffuse enlargement or abscess formation, frequently mimicking malignancy or subacute thyroiditis and complicating diagnosis^{1,2}. A systematic review emphasises that acute suppurative thyroiditis and thyroid abscess remain uncommon but potentially life-threatening, requiring prompt recognition, imaging and microbiological confirmation³.

Case report

A 70-year-old woman with pulmonary tuberculosis, ulcerative colitis, type 2 diabetes and ischaemic heart disease presented with several weeks of progressive right-sided neck swelling, dyspnoea and odynophagia, associated with night sweats and approximately 10 kg weight loss over three months. There was no history of thyroid disease. Medications included anti-tuberculous therapy, mesalazine, candesartan and metformin.

On examination, a 5-cm right-sided neck mass (level II) was palpable and did not move with swallowing; a supraclavicular node was also palpable. Vital signs were stable and there was no stridor. Thyroid function tests

were within normal limits. Ultrasonography showed a 5-cm lesion arising from the thyroid. Fine-needle aspiration of the thyroid lesion was non-diagnostic; aspiration from a supraclavicular node confirmed tuberculosis on cytology/microbiology. Given compressive symptoms and suspected suppuration, operative drainage with total thyroidectomy was undertaken and specimens were submitted for histopathology.

Figure 1: Intra-operative view showing pus collection and thyroid gland.

Figure 2: Gross specimen of the excised thyroid gland demonstrating caseation and necrosis.

Discussion

Thyroid tuberculosis is rare even in high-burden settings and may present with a spectrum from inflammatory nodules to frank abscess^{1,2}. Distinguishing infection from neoplasia or subacute thyroiditis relies on imaging and targeted sampling. In series of acute suppurative thyroiditis and abscess, recommended management comprises early broad-spectrum antimicrobial therapy directed by cultures, image-guided aspiration or percutaneous/surgical drainage, and, selectively, thyroidectomy for large or complicated collections^{3,4}. Where thyroid cytology is equivocal, sampling of involved cervical lymph nodes can establish the diagnosis, as in this case. Standard anti-tuberculous therapy remains the cornerstone of treatment for mycobacterial disease, with surgery reserved for compressive symptoms, airway threat, failure of percutaneous control or uncertainty of diagnosis^{1,3,4}. Broader endocrine surgery data from low- and middle-income settings reinforce the importance of context-appropriate pathways and follow-up⁵.

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